

Solid state synthesis of rare earth orthochromite $\text{La}_{(1-x)}\text{Sm}_x\text{CrO}_3$ nanoperovskite with its dopant concentrations

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Abstract:

The systematic solid state synthesis and investigation of rare earth orthochromites $\text{La}_{(1-x)}\text{Sm}_x\text{CrO}_3$ ($x \approx 0, 0.2$ and 0.4) have been reported. The polycrystalline $\text{La}_{(1-x)}\text{Sm}_x\text{CrO}_3$ (LSCO) nanoperovskite materials were known to be in a single phase orthorhombic crystal system and maintained its inherent octahedral distortions for the observed tolerance factor ($0.8 \leq T \leq 0.9$). Phonon Raman modes were assigned and correlated with the structure of synthesized LSCO nanoperovskite. Relative doping of samarium results in blue shift emission around $\lambda \approx 3$ nm from that of parent LaCrO_3 nanoperovskite. The change in respective properties of synthesized LSCO nanoperovskite is mostly attributed to the coulombic interaction with respect to their relative ionic radii. Elemental analysis confirms the presence of stoichiometric dopants for respective LSCO orthochromites. The finer particles tend to aggregate with a decrease of samarium dopants onto the lattice sites of LaCrO_3 nanoperovskite as inferred from microscopy studies. Magnetization analysis shows that feeble antiferromagnetism exhibited by parent has been observed due to the effective introduction of increasing samarium dopants.

References:

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